

ILLUSTRATION OF THE PLACIDIAN MECHANISM OF ACTION

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Example of Kodiak, AK

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Because every cusp is identical to the diametrically opposite cusp, we show the part of the astrograph that underlines the characterisation of the method: the *uninterrupted* and *simultaneous* recognition of all hourlines or diurnal arcs. Hence ABRAHAM IBN EZRA’s description: “the method of rising times”¹, even though said method of house division carries with it the name of the individual who divulged it, not of those who discovered it (PTOLEMY, 2nd century) or developed it trigonometrically² (GIOVANI ANTONIO MAGINI, 16th century).

¹ Following Shlomo Sela’s 2014 BRILL translation of Ezra’s *Book of Nativities and of Revolutions* (pp. 377, 404, 406).

² Makeshift of the method, not the method itself, as we would have explained later.

LEGEND OR KEY

ST = SEASONAL TIME. It indicates the amount of time that the degrees referred to in the **left** column remained **above** the horizon (at Kodiak) and the amount of time that the degrees referred to in the **right** column remained **below** the horizon (at Kodiak), as the amount of time that a point of the ecliptic (i.e. zodiacal degree) spends above the horizon is exactly the amount time that the diametrically opposite degree spends below the horizon. Put another way, the ascensional or seasonal time of a degree at any one latitude is exactly the same ascensional or seasonal time as that of the diametrically opposite degree at the diametrically opposite latitude.³

SH = SEASONAL HOURS. It indicates the **ascensional time interval** or the rate at which that degree or ecliptic point moves from one house cusp to the other *above* or *below* the horizon, upon the case.

³ Please note that the amount of time of each or any zodiacal degree above or below the horizon is the amount of time spent by the sun above or below it, upon the case, when it occupies said point of the ecliptic, that is, when it is that day of the year at a given latitude (Kodiak, in this case). Please note as well that one equal, standard, common, or coordinate hour is 1/24 of a day and is the duration measured by the passage of 15° of the equator (one time zone) past the horizon. This hour is **not** the same as a solar or seasonal hour, which is 1/12 of the actual length or amount of daylight or of nighttime at a given latitude on a given day (sometimes referred to as an “equinoctial hour,” for, during the equinox, the equal hour and the seasonal hour coincide).

SEASONAL OR ASCENSIONAL TIMES OF ALL CUSPAL DEGREES (57°N)

Measurement	Ecliptic point	ST 12/24	2 SH = 1/6	Ecliptic point	Measurement
<i>above the horizon</i>	<i>above the horizon</i>	<i>above/below the horizon</i>	<i>above/below the horizon</i>	<i>below the horizon</i>	<i>below the horizon</i>
ASC degree	00° ♌ 00'	16 h 42 min 12 s	167 min 2 s	00° ♎ 00'	DES degree
12 th cusp	25° ♊ 48'	17 h 43 min 48 s	177 min 18 s	25° ♍ 48'	6 th cusp
11 th cusp	06° ♉ 27'	14 h 59 min 18 s	149 min 53 s	06° ♋ 27'	5 th cusp
10 th cusp	26° ♛ 15'	11 h 39 min 6 s	116 min 31 s	26° ♏ 15'	4 th cusp
9 th cusp	00° ♛ 38'	9 h 31 min 18 s	95 min 13 s	00° ♏ 38'	3 rd cusp
8 th cusp	13° ♎ 14'	8 h 8 min 54 s	81 min 29 s	13° ♌ 14'	2 nd cusp

00° Leo 00'	rises at	4:30:05	12 August
25° Gemini 48'	rose <i>above</i> the horizon at	1:32:47	12 August
06° Taurus 27'	rose <i>above</i> the horizon at	23:30:20	11 August
26° Pisces 15'	rose <i>above</i> the horizon at	22:40:30	11 August
00° Pisces 38'	rose <i>above</i> the horizon at	22:09:15	11 August
13° Aquarius 14'	rose <i>above</i> the horizon at	21:42:38	11 August
00° Aquarius 00'	rests at	4:30:05	12 August
25° Sagittarius 48'	rested <i>below</i> the horizon at	1:32:47	12 August
06° Scorpio 27'	rested <i>below</i> the horizon at	23:30:20	11 August
26° Virgo 15'	rested <i>below</i> the horizon at	22:40:30	11 August
00° Virgo 38'	rested <i>below</i> the horizon at	22:09:15	11 August
13° Leo 14'	rested <i>below</i> the horizon at	21:42:38	11 August

Times spent above or below the horizon remain the same at said latitude regardless of the time of year.

PREDICTION OR HYPOTHESIS

00° Leo 00' will appear at the subsequent cusps above the horizon every two diurnal seasonal hours — of that degree — after the time of birth. The diametrically opposite degree, 00° Aquarius 00', for its part, will exhibit the same behaviour, although below the horizon. That is, zero degrees of Aquarius would move to each of the subsequent cusps below the horizon every two nocturnal seasonal hours of that degree. The same should be true to **any other** Placidus-measured cuspal degree, as long as the measurement or calculation of the astrography is done naturally, i.e. as long as it respects the seasonal time. This calculation is none other than the method of primary displacement or motion, better known as Placidus⁴.

⁴ The method is named after Placidus of Titis, the Benedictine monk who divulged the method during the seventeenth century, although it was originally employed by Abraham ibn Ezra in the twelfth century and trigonometrically developed by Giovanni Antonio Magini in the sixteenth century. Ezra, however, made reference to Ptolemy (second century) when discussing this method, although Ptolemy did not employ it for the purpose of astrographical or horoscope construction, but for the purpose of determining the life span of the native. Contrary to popular belief, then, this method is not only not modern (but ancient), but also possibly the oldest method of quadrant house division, as the houses of Porphyry (considered to constitute the first quadrant house system) correspond to the third century AD. Finally, it is necessary to mention that the **trigonometric** version of the method is not the method itself but an approximation of it (i.e. “makeshift”, as Michael Wackford has maintained in *Correlation*, 2001) in order to be able to provide the tables of convenience for the purposes of erecting the chart. Because the method is essentially physical (seasonal times or multiple diurnal arcs — or time lines — to be discerned simultaneously and uninterruptedly), its mathematical expression is particularly difficult. All criticisms against Placidus in the polar regions, for example, are unfounded in the sense that what is criticised is not the method itself but its trigonometric expression (unknowingly which we consider shameful, not only unfortunate).

DEMONSTRATION I

00° Leo 00' and **00° Aquarius 00'** move, simultaneously, at a **167 min 2 s** rate *above* and *below* the horizon, respectively, amount of time which constitutes two *diurnal* and *nocturnal* seasonal hours (2 h 47 min 2 s), respectively, of said degrees or points of the ecliptic:

Ecliptic point	House cusp	Time	House cusp	Ecliptic point
00° ♌ 00'	1 st House cusp	4:30:05	7 th House cusp	00° ♎ 00'
00° ♌ 00'	12 th House cusp	7:17:07	2 nd House cusp	00° ♎ 00'
00° ♌ 00'	11 th House cusp	10:04:09	3 rd House cusp	00° ♎ 00'
00° ♌ 00'	10 th House cusp	12:51:11	4 th House cusp	00° ♎ 00'
00° ♌ 00'	9 th House cusp	15:38:13	5 th House cusp	00° ♎ 00'
00° ♌ 00'	8 th House cusp	6:25:15	6 th House cusp	00° ♎ 00'
00° ♌ 00'	7 th House cusp	21:12:17	1 st House cusp	00° ♎ 00'

DEMONSTRATION II

25° Gemini 48' and **25° Sagittarius 48'** move, simultaneously, at a **177 min 18 s** rate *above* and *below* the horizon, respectively, amount of time which constitutes two *diurnal* and *nocturnal* seasonal hours (2 h 57 min 18 s), respectively, of said degrees or points of the ecliptic:

Ecliptic point	House cusp	Time	House cusp	Ecliptic point
25° ♊ 48'	1 st House cusp	1:32:47	7 th House cusp	25° ♏ 48'
25° ♊ 48'	12 th House cusp	04:30:05	2 nd House cusp	25° ♏ 48'
25° ♊ 48'	11 th House cusp	07:27:23	3 rd House cusp	25° ♏ 48'
25° ♊ 48'	10 th House cusp	10:24:41	4 th House cusp	25° ♏ 48'
25° ♊ 48'	9 th House cusp	13:21:52	5 th House cusp	25° ♏ 48'
25° ♊ 48'	8 th House cusp	16:19:10	6 th House cusp	25° ♏ 48'
25° ♊ 48'	7 th House cusp	19:16:28	1 st House cusp	25° ♏ 48'

CORROBORATE THE RESULTS

Whatever zodiacal degree (i.e. point on the ecliptic) we select, we will always see it traverse or appear at the subsequent cusps every two seasonal hours — of that degree — thereafter. The reader can corroborate this by using the *Animate* feature of the software. Once we click on *Animate*, another window will appear, in whose *Step by* space we will type in the number of minutes that constitutes the rate at which that degree moves (above or below the horizon) according to our table originally presented, and we will have verified for ourselves

the natural integrity of the “method of rising times” (ABRAHAM IBN EZRA)⁵.

⁵ English translation of “method of rising times,” according to the 2014 English translation by Shlomo Sela, BRILL edition, pp. 377, 404, 406.

CONCLUSION

Both the tables and the exercises corroborating or confirming the information contained in them demonstrate that each house **measures a different amount of time** than the previous house and the house that follows within the same hemisphere (higher or lower, upon the case). In other words, each cuspal degree (even each degree of the ecliptic or zodiacal belt) **represents a different ascensional or seasonal time**, that which the sun exhibited or had when it occupied that point of the ecliptic at that latitude. This is the reason for which, without regard to the cuspal degree selected, it will necessarily appear on or as the subsequent house cusp exactly two seasonal hours — of that degree — later. Every zodiacal degree retains the time marked or established by the sun the first time it occupied that point of the ecliptic at that latitude, for which reason, **in spite of also the time of year** (i.e. the degree occupied by the sun in the birthchart), that cuspal degree will **continue** to behave in the same way (i.e. as the sun did when it occupied that degree at that latitude). Only a **natural measurement** of the astrographic regions, however, can reflect such a rhythm, cycle, or displacement. Herein lies the reason for which one can speak of a natural compatibility or of a perfect equivalence between such a method of house division and solar or seasonal hours (perhaps confusingly regarded as *planetary* hours). The Placidus method of house division may or should, therefore, be regarded as the «timekeeping» method of house division or, as ABRAHAM IBN EZRA expressed during the twelfth century, “the method of rising times” (trans. SHLOMO SELA, 2014, Brill).⁶

⁶ Because each degree has *its own* ascensional time, we have also elsewhere proposed that it be regarded as the method of **proper times** (relativistic term). For more information on this, please see “Time Dilation according to Tropical Astrology and Why the Placidus Measurement of Astrographic Regions is Compatible with Relativity Theory” at <https://zenodo.org/records/13902128> (DOI 10.5281/zenodo.13841957) and this [video](#) (brilliant visual illustration by Dave Feldman, professor of Physics and of Mathematics). The following, however, should always be borne in mind. There are two forms or expressions of relativity or time dilation, special (1905) and general (1915). Whilst the first phenomenon hinges upon speed, the second upon gravity. The first form or expression of relativity known to mankind,

EPILOGUE

The rigour of the Placidus method rests upon the **exhaustiveness** that characterises the exercise of searching for ascensional times, that is, on the registration or record-keeping of the seasonal or ascensional time of all the oblique or zodiacal degrees, which will reveal which will occupy the intermediate cusps (i.e. diurnal arcs or hourlines). In this respect, it distinguishes or sets itself apart from the other two well-known time-orientated methods of house division, Alcabitius and Koch, from the point of views of both its rigour and naturalism. The **Alcabitius** and **Koch** calculations record the seasonal time of only the ascending degree and of the culminating degree, respectively, in order to divide that amount of time into three equal parts. Expounded differently, the intermediate cusps constitute one third of the time of the ascending degree (Alcabitius) or of the culminating degree (Koch), so that the twelfth (12), eleventh (11), and tenth (10) houses measure exactly the same amount of time under both calculations, and likewise the ninth, eighth, and seventh houses, for the exercise described above in relation to the ascensional or seasonal time of these degrees (ASC and MC) is repeated below the horizon (i.e. from the IC to the ASC, diametrically opposite quadrant to the one from the MC to the DES). Our exposition, in turn, demonstrates, unequivocally so, that each house *measures the result of the trisection of a different ascensional time*, that of *that* cuspal degree (not that of the ASC, as in Alcabitius, nor that of the MC, as in Koch). They all have **relative** times (or fixed relative times, since they are always the same at a given latitude). This is the reason why it is the only method naturally compatible with both seasonal times and relativity (i.e. time

however, is constituted by tropical astronomy (see 'equation of time') and, although velocity *is* a variable, this relativistic modality is due to the tilt of a moving frame of reference, the Earth, relative to an inertial frame of reference, the ecliptic or the zodiacal belt. The timekeeping method of house division (i.e. Placidus) teaches it to us in the sense that it allows us to make the corroboration aforementioned in this presentation (i.e. seasonal hours of different cuspal degrees) without the sun occupying said points of our ecliptic.

is not absolute, as the other two calculations mentioned above would appear to lead one to believe).

Placidus also provides the necessary evidence to support the fact that we can consider an astrography to have three hundred and sixty (sub)angles and to be composed of twelve instead of four, even if four, not twelve, are the most important, relevant, or sensitive and we refer to the rest by another name, not 'angle'. That a US state or a country of the UK has four borders, for example, means not that the lines distinguishing the jurisdiction of police and judges within the state or country are not relevant. The relevance of some lines (cusps) versus the relevance of other lines (cusps) may differ in nature, purpose, or objective.

That they vary in nature, however, does not detract from their relevance: to define or decide, determine or distinguish with clarity where the jurisdiction of a planet within a quadrant begins and ends (as we distinguish where the jurisdiction of a police force or judicial authority begins and ends based also on imaginary physical lines). Does it extend beyond the tenth house if the degree of the ecliptic it occupies is four or six degrees (of the same sign) from the subsequent cusp (as LILLY and MORIN, among others, have taught)? If so, is it really six degrees or is it less than six degrees, or is it more than six degrees? This will decide whether that planet exerts its influence also over the house that follows, in which case the affairs of the house may be considered to be affected by an additional celestial body, as it would have rights over those affairs by virtue of the position it occupies within the chart.

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